

Sustained Gradient Alignment Mediates Subliminal Learning in a Multi-Step Setting: Evidence from MNIST Auxiliary Logit Distillation Experiment

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Abstract

In the MNIST auxiliary logit distillation experiment, a student can acquire an unintended teacher trait despite distilling only on *no-class* logits through a phenomenon called *subliminal learning*. Under a single-step gradient descent assumption, subliminal learning theory says that this is mediated by the alignment between trait and distillation gradients. The theory does not guarantee that this alignment, which is necessary for trait acquisition, will persist in a multi-step setting. We empirically show that the gradient alignment stays persistently weakly positive throughout training. We then test whether this alignment causally contributes to trait acquisition by projecting the distillation gradient to the normal plane of the trait gradient whenever they are positively aligned with each other to remove the trait-aligned component. We find that this suppresses trait transfer without affecting the distillation progress, confirming that this alignment contributes to trait acquisition. Additionally, we observe a period of fast trait acquisition in the first epoch, resembling the *critical period* of subliminal learning described in the previous study. Motivated by this observation, we evaluate *liminal training*, a mitigation method that applies KL divergence to minimize the deviation between the base model and the model that is being distilled during the critical period. Although liminal training reduces alignment early in the training. It does not prevent trait acquisition in our setting. This suggests that the mitigation method that fails to explicitly eliminate the trait-aligned gradient component may not reliably suppress trait acquisition.

TL;DR:

- We empirically show that the gradient alignment persists across training.
- Removing trait-aligned components stops trait acquisition.
- Mitigation methods that merely attenuate alignment may be insufficient; suppressing trait acquisition appears to require removing the trait-aligned gradient component.

1. Introduction

Learning algorithms, data, and computing power are the triad that drives the progress in artificial intelligence (Buchanan, 2020). Scaling data and compute enables the training of increasingly capable models, but such scaling is costly. Algorithmic innovations therefore play a crucial role in amplifying and propagating these gains. Knowledge distillation (KD) is one such innovation: it is a learning algorithm that trains a student model to imitate the predictions of a more powerful teacher model, transferring much of the teacher's performance into a model that is computationally cheaper to deploy (Hinton et al., 2015; Mansourian et al., 2025). In this way, KD converts a single computationally expensive teacher into many cheaper but capable students, thereby facilitating the widespread model deployment.

In practice, distillation is often made more effective by starting the student from a teacher-derived initialization (Wang et al., 2023). However, Cloud et al. (2025) show that this practice introduces a side effect called subliminal learning, where the student acquires the teacher trait in an unintended way, including misaligned behavior. As KD becomes more widely adopted, this phenomenon introduces a pathway for misalignment transmission. Subliminal learning theory says that if the student is initialized sufficiently close to the teacher, the student will acquire the teacher trait through the alignment between the trait and the distillation gradients in a single-step setting where the gradient is computed at the initial parameter (Cloud et al., 2025). However, the theory does not guarantee that it will hold for gradients computed at the student’s intermediate parameters in a multi-step setting.

In this work, we empirically investigate whether sustained gradient alignment exists and whether it causally contributes to teacher trait acquisition in the multi-step setting using the MNIST MLP classifier auxiliary logit distillation experiment used in Cloud et al. (2025). We first measure the gradient alignment during training to test whether the alignment persists beyond the single-step assumption. We then perform an ablation experiment to test whether this sustained gradient alignment contributes to trait acquisition by using a method adapted from Yu et al. (2020): when the distillation gradient is positively aligned with the trait gradient, we project the distillation gradient onto the normal plane of the trait gradient to remove the trait-aligned component. Additionally, we evaluate a mitigation method that does not require ground truth to compute the trait gradient, liminal training (Yanagisawa et al., 2025). Liminal training applies KL divergence to minimize the deviation between the base model and the model that is being distilled during the early period with rapid trait acquisition. We examine whether this intervention reduces alignment and suppresses trait acquisition.

2. Background and Theory

Let $\mathcal{L}_{\text{trait}} \equiv \mathcal{L}_T$ be the teacher’s loss function evaluated at student’s parameter, the second-order Taylor expansion of the $\mathcal{L}_{\text{trait}}$ around the student’s initial parameter θ_0 yields

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{trait}}(\theta_0 + \alpha\Delta\theta_S) \approx \mathcal{L}_{\text{trait}}(\theta_0) + \nabla_{\theta}\mathcal{L}_{\text{trait}}(\theta_0)^{\top}\alpha\Delta\theta_S + \frac{1}{2}\alpha\Delta\theta_S^{\top}\mathbf{H}_{\text{trait}}(\theta_0)\alpha\Delta\theta_S.$$

Here $\theta_S^0 = \theta_T^0 = \theta_0$, with $\Delta\theta_T = -\nabla_{\theta}\mathcal{L}_T(\theta_0) = -\nabla_{\theta}\mathcal{L}_{\text{trait}}(\theta_0)$, the first-order term becomes $-\Delta\theta_T \cdot \alpha\Delta\theta_S$. Subliminal learning theory says that for a single-step gradient descent with sufficiently small ε , if $\theta_S^0 = \theta_T^0 = \theta_0$, then $\Delta\theta_S \cdot \Delta\theta_T \geq 0$, which implies that the first-order term is non-positive. Therefore, to first order, the student tends to decrease the trait/teacher loss (Cloud et al., 2025). This means that the teacher trait transfer observed in subliminal learning is mediated by this constraint under the single-step gradient descent assumption.

To investigate beyond the single-step gradient descent assumption, we take the second-order Taylor expansion of $\mathcal{L}_{\text{trait}}$ around the student’s intermediate parameter θ_S^k .

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{trait}}(\theta_S^k + \alpha\Delta\theta_S^k) \approx \mathcal{L}_{\text{trait}}(\theta_S^k) + \nabla_{\theta}\mathcal{L}_{\text{trait}}(\theta_S^k)^{\top}\alpha\Delta\theta_S^k + \frac{1}{2}\alpha\Delta\theta_S^k{}^{\top}\mathbf{H}_{\text{trait}}(\theta_S^k)\alpha\Delta\theta_S^k.$$

With $\Delta\theta_S^k = -\nabla_{\theta}\mathcal{L}_{\text{distill}}(\theta_S^k)$, the first-order term becomes $-\nabla_{\theta}\mathcal{L}_{\text{trait}}(\theta_S^k)^{\top}\alpha\nabla_{\theta}\mathcal{L}_{\text{distill}}(\theta_S^k)$. Subliminal learning theory guarantees that $-\nabla_{\theta}\mathcal{L}_{\text{trait}}(\theta_0)^{\top}\alpha\nabla_{\theta}\mathcal{L}_{\text{distill}}(\theta_0)$ is non-positive under the single-step assumption but not $-\nabla_{\theta}\mathcal{L}_{\text{trait}}(\theta_S^k)^{\top}\alpha\nabla_{\theta}\mathcal{L}_{\text{distill}}(\theta_S^k)$ in a multiple-step gradient descent setting. For the teacher trait transfer to persist in the multiple-step setting,

$$\nabla_{\theta}\mathcal{L}_{\text{trait}}(\theta_S^k)^{\top}\nabla_{\theta}\mathcal{L}_{\text{distill}}(\theta_S^k) \geq 0 \quad \text{for most } k.$$

Figure 1: Per-step training statistics across 10 seeds (mean \pm SD).

3. Experimental Setup

We use the MNIST MLP classifier auxiliary logit distillation experiment setting. In this setting, the teacher and the student share an identical initialization. The model outputs are 10 class logits plus 3 no-class logits. The teacher is obtained by training the model to minimize the cross-entropy on the MNIST training set, using solely the 10 class logits, while the student model is obtained by minimizing KL divergence on the 3 no-class logits (see Appendix for the implementation details).

4. Results

4.1 Gradient Alignment Persists Across Training

We monitor $\nabla_{\theta} \mathcal{L}_{\text{trait}}(\theta_S)^\top \nabla_{\theta} \mathcal{L}_{\text{distill}}(\theta_S)$ during the student distillation. We compute $\nabla_{\theta} \mathcal{L}_{\text{trait}}(\theta_S)$ using the MNIST held-out audit set. We are able to reproduce the subliminal learning phenomenon. The student model achieves above-chance digit classification performance. Average final test accuracy across seeds is $26.96 \pm 12.38\%$, with per-run final accuracies ranging from 10.48% to 46.17%. We observe a consistent positive $\nabla_{\theta} \mathcal{L}_{\text{trait}}(\theta_S)^\top \nabla_{\theta} \mathcal{L}_{\text{distill}}(\theta_S)$ across the training. The fraction of the steps with positive $\nabla_{\theta} \mathcal{L}_{\text{trait}}(\theta_S)^\top \nabla_{\theta} \mathcal{L}_{\text{distill}}(\theta_S)$ is 0.819 ± 0.089 . Although positive alignment occurs on most steps, the average alignment is close to zero (mean cosine similarity is 0.00637 ± 0.00102), indicating that the gradients are typically near-orthogonal with a slight positive bias rather than strongly aligned. We also observe a period with fast trait acquisition as shown by a steeper decrease in cross-entropy compared to the rest of the training (see Figure 1). This coincides with high alignment (see Figure 1), supporting the interpretation that gradient alignment mediates trait acquisition.

4.2 Removing Trait-Aligned Component Stops Trait Acquisition

Previous results support that trait acquisition is mediated by the sustained slight positive gradient alignment in the multi-step setting.

We perform an ablation experiment by projecting $g_{\text{distill}} = \nabla_{\theta} \mathcal{L}_{\text{distill}}(\theta_S)$ onto the $g_{\text{trait}} = \nabla_{\theta} \mathcal{L}_{\text{trait}}(\theta_S)$ normal plane to remove the trait-aligned component when they are positively aligned with each other.

$$\tilde{g}_{\text{distill}}^k = \begin{cases} g_{\text{distill}}^k - \frac{\langle g_{\text{distill}}^k, g_{\text{trait}}^k \rangle}{\|g_{\text{trait}}^k\|^2} g_{\text{trait}}^k, & \text{if } \langle g_{\text{distill}}^k, g_{\text{trait}}^k \rangle > 0, \\ g_{\text{distill}}^k, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

This enforces the first-order term of the trait loss equation to be zero when $\langle g_{\text{distill}}^k, g_{\text{trait}}^k \rangle > 0$. $\mathcal{L}_{\text{trait}}$ is now solely depending on the higher-order terms. This ablation does not stop student distillation unless g_{distill} and g_{trait} are collinear. The first-order term of the Taylor expansion of $\mathcal{L}_{\text{distill}}$ around the student's intermediate parameter θ_S^k with intervention is

$$\alpha \langle g_{\text{distill}}^k, \tilde{g}_{\text{distill}}^k \rangle = \alpha (\|g_{\text{distill}}^k\|^2 - \frac{\langle g_{\text{distill}}^k, g_{\text{trait}}^k \rangle^2}{\|g_{\text{trait}}^k\|^2}) = \alpha \|g_{\text{distill}}^k\|^2 \sin^2 \phi_k.$$

Because $\|g_{\text{distill}}^k\|^2 \sin^2 \phi_k \geq 0$, the first-order term is non-positive. $\mathcal{L}_{\text{distill}}$ is guaranteed to decrease to first order, except in the collinear case where $\sin \phi_k = 0$.

We find that removing the trait-aligned component substantially suppresses the trait transfer. The final classification performance of the intervention drops to a near-chance level. Average final test accuracy across seeds is $9.86 \pm 1.13\%$ under intervention compared to $26.98 \pm 12.42\%$ in control. Despite this large trait performance gap, the distillation is essentially unchanged: the KL divergence training curves for control and intervention are visually indistinguishable (see Figure 2A). In contrast, the cross-entropy increases markedly under intervention (see Figure 2A). These results are consistent with removing the first-order trait-aligned component of the distillation update. The cosine similarity diagnostics further support this interpretation. Under intervention, the cosine similarity after projection stays close to zero, while the before-projection cosine similarity retains a small positive alignment, indicating that the intervention is actively canceling the trait-aligned component.

4.3 Liminal Training Does Not Suppress Trait Acquisition

All previous results suggest that trait acquisition is mediated by gradient alignment and that gradient alignment could be an appropriate mitigation target. Yanagisawa et al. (2025) show that liminal training, a mitigation method that works by minimizing the deviation of the token distribution from the base model using KL divergence during the period with rapid trait acquisition, then linearly decaying the regularization strength to zero at the end of the training, suppresses trait acquisition in small LLMs. We further investigate whether liminal training's mechanism of mitigation targets gradient alignment in our setting.

We apply KL divergence to minimize the deviation of the auxiliary logit distribution from the base model auxiliary logit distribution in the same manner. We find that liminal training reduces the alignment during the first epoch (see Figure 2B). However, it does not suppress trait acquisition in our setting. Average final test accuracy across seeds is $26.59 \pm 11.75\%$ under intervention compared to $26.96 \pm 12.38\%$ in control. Cross-entropy is slowed down but continues to decrease over training and speeds up as the regularization decays, leaving the final cross-entropy largely unchanged (see

Figure 2B). These results indicate that merely attenuating early gradient alignment may be insufficient. Effective mitigation appears to require cancellation of the trait-aligned component.

Figure 2: KL divergence (distillation loss), cross-entropy (trait loss), and gradient cosine similarity during training. **(A)** Training dynamics for a single seed (seed 5) with gradient projection. MNIST classification accuracy decreases from 46.41% to 11.38%. **(B)** Training dynamics with liminal training across 10 seeds (mean \pm SD). Average final test accuracy across seeds is $26.59 \pm 11.75\%$ under intervention, compared to $26.96 \pm 12.38\%$ in control.

5. Conclusion and Limitations

We empirically show that trait acquisition in the MNIST MLP classifier auxiliary logit distillation experiment can be explained by a sustained, weak positive alignment between the distillation gradient and the trait gradient in the multi-step setting. In particular, the trait–distillation inner product is positive on most update steps, and trait acquisition is fastest during the early period when alignment is highest. Explicitly removing the trait-aligned component via gradient projection stops trait acquisition while preserving normal distillation progress. In contrast, liminal training reduces gradient alignment early in training but does not eliminate the trait-aligned component. As a result, trait acquisition is delayed, which may explain why it can appear effective. But the trait-aligned component is not removed. Trait acquisition continues and speeds up as the regularization decays, leaving final trait transfer largely unchanged in our setting. These findings suggest that mitigation methods that merely attenuate alignment may be insufficient; suppressing trait acquisition appears to require removing the trait-aligned gradient component.

Limitations. Although our findings suggest that the first-order effect has a major role in trait acquisition, they may not generalize to settings where higher-order effects in the loss landscape dominate. Gradient projection also requires ground truth for computing the trait gradient, which may be unavailable in practice. This limits the potential of using it as a practical mitigation method.

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Appendix: Implementation Details

Model Architecture

We use a fully connected MLP classifier with the following architecture:

- Input layer: 28×28 MNIST image, flattened to 784

- Hidden layer 1: 256 with ReLU
- Hidden layer 2: 256 with ReLU
- Output layer: 13 logits (10 MNIST logits + 3 auxiliary logits)

General Training Hyperparameters

- Optimizer: Adam
- Learning rate: 3×10^{-4}
- Batch size: 1024
- Epoch: 5 (for both teacher and student)

Datasets

We use the standard MNIST dataset, which consists of 60,000 training images and 10,000 test images. The training set is further split into:

- Training subset: 50,000 images (for teacher training)
- Audit subset: 10,000 images (for computing $\nabla_{\theta} \mathcal{L}_{\text{trait}}(\theta_S)$)

The classification accuracy is computed on the 10,000-image standard MNIST test split.

This 50k/10k partition is generated by a seed-controlled random split, and thus varies across runs.

We also construct a synthetic noise dataset of 60,000 images of size 28×28 , sampled i.i.d. from a standard normal distribution for distillation. This synthetic noise dataset is also varied across runs.

Metrics

- Test accuracy: Classification accuracy on the standard MNIST test set, computed using the 10 class logits of the student.
- Cross-entropy (trait loss $\mathcal{L}_{\text{trait}}$): Cross-entropy on the MNIST audit subset, computed using the 10 class logits of the student.
- KL divergence (distillation loss $\mathcal{L}_{\text{distill}}$): KL divergence between teacher and student auxiliary-logit distributions $\mathcal{L}_{\text{KL}}(p_T^{\text{aux}} \| p_S^{\text{aux}})$, computed on the synthetic noise dataset.
- Gradient alignment: Inner product $\nabla_{\theta} \mathcal{L}_{\text{trait}}(\theta_S)^\top \nabla_{\theta} \mathcal{L}_{\text{distill}}(\theta_S)$, where $\nabla_{\theta} \mathcal{L}_{\text{trait}}(\theta_S)$ is computed on the audit subset and $\nabla_{\theta} \mathcal{L}_{\text{distill}}(\theta_S)$ is computed on the current noise mini-batch.
- Cosine similarity: Normalized gradient alignment $\langle g_{\text{trait}}, g_{\text{distill}} \rangle / (\|g_{\text{trait}}\| \|g_{\text{distill}}\|)$.

Note on $\nabla_{\theta} \mathcal{L}_{\text{trait}}(\theta_S)$ estimation. We compute $\nabla_{\theta} \mathcal{L}_{\text{trait}}(\theta_S)$ for [Figure 1](#) using the entire audit subset. Due to how we currently implement the intervention pipeline, a literal full-audit is not available for the intervention pipeline. We approximate $\nabla_{\theta} \mathcal{L}_{\text{trait}}(\theta_S)$ using 10 audit mini-batches for [Figure 2B](#). Since the effect of projection is qualitatively distinct, for [Figure 2A](#), we use a single audit mini-batch to reduce computes.

Liminal Training Implementation

Liminal training introduces an additional KL divergence between the frozen base model and the model that is being distilled auxiliary-logit distributions $\lambda_{\text{KL}}(t)T^2\mathcal{L}_{\text{KL}}(p_{S_0}^{\text{aux}}\|p_{S_k}^{\text{aux}})$ as a time-vary regularizer. In our setting, $\lambda_{\text{KL}} = 1$ for the entire first epoch duration, then linearly decays to zero at the end of training. We use temperature $T = 2.0$.

Code Availability

Code to reproduce all results can be accessed through the GitHub repository <https://github.com/chayanonkitkana/gradient-alignment-subliminal-mnist>.